

agroecological situations, seed quality also varies.

We studied the variability in seeds produced from different tillers in a plant, between plants in a population, and between populations produced in different parts of the Cauvery Delta Zone. Five varieties were tested: short-duration IR50, ADT36, and TKM9; medium-duration IR20; and long-duration CR1009.

Ten locations were selected, with 10 fields sampled in each location. For tiller and plant analysis, 10 clumps/field were used.

Seeds were collected at maturity and germinated in the laboratory. Percentage germination and seedling length were multiplied to calculate the vigor index. The results were pooled by location.

Between tillers and plants, variability was higher in seedling vigor than in germination. Variability in both germinability and seedling vigor was

almost equal across locations, irrespective of variety. Mean variability in germination and seedling vigor was 8.4 and 18% among tillers, 5 and 10% among plants in a population, and 23 and 24% among locations.

The higher variability between tillers than between plants might be due to different times of tillering (varying with water level) and times of anthesis and seed maturation. The difference

among locations might be due to different soil conditions, dates of sowing, and other environmental components.

Among the varieties, variability in seed germination among tillers was highest in CR1009; that among locations was highest in AD736 (Table 1). Variability in seedling vigor between tillers was highest in TKM9 (Table 2). □

Table 1. Variation in seed germination between tillers of a plant, plants in a population, and production locations. Tamil Nadu, India.

Variety	Variation (%) in seed germination		
	Between tillers	Between plants	Between locations
IR50	7	5	21
ADT36	10	6	28
TKM9	4	2	24
IR20	7	6	20
CR1009	14	5	22
Mean	8.4	5	23
LSD: 3			

Table 2. Variation in seedling vigor between tillers of a plant, plants in a population, and location. Tamil Nadu, India.

Variety	Variation (%) in seedling vigor		
	Between tillers	Between plants	Between locations
IR50	18	10	22
ADT36	16	9	21
TKM9	22	14	36
IR20	16	8	20
CR1009	18	10	23
Mean	18	10	24
LSD: 4			

Minimizing intravarietal variation in rice experiments

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Large variations in many morphological characters are observed within rice cultivars in field and greenhouse trials, even under uniform growing conditions. One reason may be differences in seed quality. We experimented with seeds of three varieties.

Bulk seeds of IR30, IR32385-37-3-3, and IR28211-43-1-1 (105-110 d) were harvested in 1988 dry season. Dried seeds were graded into poor, good, and high-density (HD) grains using distilled water and salt solutions of varying specific gravity. Seeds of each grade were separated into embryo, endosperm, and hull.

Total grain weights were similar, except in IR28211-43-1-1 (Table 1). Embryo weights of HD grains were significantly heavier than those of poor grains in all cultivars. In IR28211-43-1-1, embryo weights of the grades

differed significantly: large, heavy seeds had heavy embryos. Endosperm weights did not differ between good and HD grains, but were significantly heavier for both grades than for poor grain. Hull weight differed among grades in IR30 and IR28211-43-1-1.

Seeds of the three grades were sown in 4-liter pots containing 3 kg of

Maahas clay soil with added fertilizers, in a randomized block design with three replications and raised in the greenhouse.

At 25 DAS, seedlings from good and HD grains were significantly taller than those from poor grains. For most characters, the trends in IR30 and IR32385-37-3-3 were similar. In

Table 1. Characteristics of seeds of different quality.^a

Grain grade ^b	Weight (mg) per 100 grains			
	Embryo	Endosperm	Hull	Total
	<i>IR30</i>			
Poor	13.2 a	341.6 a	350.8 a	705.6 a
Good	17.9 b	1385.7 b	403.2 b	1807.3 b
High density	18.4 b	1549.6 b	438.0 c	2005.5 b
	<i>IR32385-37-3-3</i>			
Poor	23.7 a	908.3 a	351.4 a	1283.4 a
Good	25.5 ab	1481.9 b	407.9 b	1915.3 b
High density	27.1 b	1600.2 b	419.7 b	2047.0 b
	<i>IR28211-43-1-1</i>			
Poor	16.8 a	884.6 a	384.3 a	1285.7 a
Good	25.0 b	1626.2 b	441.0 b	2092.2 b
High density	29.4 c	1909.1 b	498.7 c	2437.2 c

^aMeans followed by a common letter in a column are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. ^bPoor = sp gr ≤ 1.0, good = sp gr > 1.0-≤ 1.20, high density = sp gr > 1.20.

IR28211-43-1-1, all characters but leaf dry weight differed significantly among grades. Differences in IR28211-43-1-1 were greater because differences among embryo weights were larger.

Mean data show significant differences among grades for all traits except plant height and specific leaf weight. The coefficient of variation for growth parameters was much lower for HD grains (Table 2) than for poor and good grains. This indicates that intravarietal or intragenotype variation can be lessened by planting HD grains. □

Table 2. Coefficient of variation for growth parameters of different grain grades at 25 d after sowing.

Grain grade	Coefficient of variation						
	Plant height	Tiller no.	Leaf area	Specific leafweight	Leaf dry weight	Culm dry weight	Total dry weight
	<i>IR30</i>						
Poor	13.2	48.0	33.6	31.6	30.4	31.2	30.8
Good	10.1	35.6	31.7	25.8	27.1	26.4	26.7
High density	11.3	22.1	27.2	20.2	20.3	22.3	21.3
	<i>IR32385-37-3-3</i>						
Poor	12.0	34.4	40.1	40.0	76.3	38.2	57.2
Good	4.4	16.1	21.5	16.7	16.5	17.5	17.0
High density	6.7	17.3	18.2	17.4	16.8	17.1	16.9
	<i>IR28211-13-1-1</i>						
Poor	23.0	21.7	25.1	21.0	21.1	21.1	25.1
Good	6.1	18.4	23.4	19.1	19.9	18.3	23.9
High density	3.5	15.8	16.8	16.1	19.2	13.1	13.1

Path analysis of rice grain yield under rainfed lowland conditions

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We examined direct and indirect associations of four yield components with grain yield in drought-tolerant lines MDU1, Brown gora, BR319-1, OS4, E45, C22, OS6, IR12979-24-1-8, UPLRi-5, UPLRi-7, Azucena, N22, and Kalakeri and local check PMK1 grown in semidry conditions in 1988.

The trial was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications.

Productive tillers had high direct effects on grain yield (see table). Panicle length and flowering duration had moderate direct effects. The effect

of plant height was slightly negative.

Productive tillers appear to be the most reliable character to use in selecting genotypes under rainfed condition. □

Path analysis showing direct and indirect effects of yield components on grain yield under rainfed lowland semidry conditions.^a Madurai, Tamil Nadu, India, 1988.

Variable	Flowering duration	Plant height	Panicle length	Productive tillers	Total correlation with yield
Flowering duration	<u>0.250</u>	0.006	0.161	-0.255	0.162
Plant height	-0.085	<u>-0.016</u>	-0.150	-0.109	-0.361
Panicle length	0.130	0.008	<u>0.310</u>	-0.598	-0.150
Productive tillers	-0.063	0.002	-0.183	<u>0.992</u>	0.748**

^a Residual effect = 0.471. Underlined correlations indicate direct effects. ** = significant at P = 0.01.

Varietal differences in rice ratoon performance

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The success of rice ratooning depends primarily on the variety used. We compared medium-duration rice varieties Ponni and Bhavani in sandy clay loam soils during the wet season.

The main crop was harvested 15 cm from ground level and the stubble fertilized with 100-50-50 kg NPK/ha.

Bhavani was significantly superior to Ponni on all growth and yield attributes (see table). The Bhavani ratoon crop yielded 2.8 t/ha—50% of its main crop

yield. Ponni produced 1.8 t/ha, 38% of its main crop yield. Straw yield in Bhavani ratoon was also higher. □

Growth and yield attributes of rice ratoon crop in Madurai, India during the wet season.

Variety	Plant height (cm)	Ratoon tillers/hill	Productive tillers/m ²	Filled grains/panicle	Thousand-grain weight (g)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Straw yield (t/ha)
Ponni	69.7	9.4	319.2	59.4	15.5	1.8	2.3
Bhavani	74.0	11.9	414.2	66.2	20.8	2.8	3.4
LSD (0.05)	1.7	0.4	9.5	2.6	0.11	0.2	0.3